

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT AND RESIDUAL STRENGTHS OF OPEN HOLE SPECIMENS IN FATIGUE

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Abstract

An extensive experimental program was carried out to investigate and understand the sequence of damage development throughout the life of open hole composite laminates loaded in tension-tension fatigue. Quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates, with stacking sequence $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_S$, $[45/90/-45/0]_{2S}$ and $[45/90/-45/0]_{4S}$ were examined. These were selected on the basis that under quasi-static loading the $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_S$ configuration exhibited a delamination dominated mode of failure whilst the $[45/90/-45/0]_{2S}$ and

$[45/90/-45/0]_{4S}$ configurations showed a fibre dominated failure mode, described as "pullout" and "brittle" respectively [1]. Specimens were fatigue loaded at 5Hz with various amplitudes to 1E6 cycles or catastrophic failure, whichever occurred first. For the laminates: $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_S$ and $[45/90/-45/0]_{2S}$ failure occurred by delamination. A number of tests were interrupted at various points as the stiffness dropped with increasing cycles. The interrupted test specimens were inspected using X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) scanning in order to accurately determine a sequence of damage events leading to failure. For the $[45/90/-45/0]_{4S}$ configuration, even the highest of severities result in little or no loss of stiffness after 1E6 cycles. A static residual strength program was carried out using each configuration.

Introduction

Fibre-reinforced composites laminates are increasingly being used to manufacture load bearing primary structures in the aerospace industry as composites offer a much greater strength to weight ratio than metals.

The initial perception was that composite materials don't suffer from the effects of fatigue, however in recent years it has become well established that composites do exhibit damage under cyclic loading conditions. Laminates with stress concentrations

have complex damage sequences and failure events, and show a wide variety of effects not observed in unnotched laminates. The notch sensitivity of a laminate in terms of mechanical properties, depends on various factors, such as: laminate thickness, ply orientations, laminate size, notch size, and machining quality. These factors all affect the way damage propagates, their interactions and the final mode of failure. In previous work, Spearing and Beaumont [2] concentrated on tension-tension fatigue of notched Carbon/Epoxy (T300/914) and Carbon/Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) laminates using an R ratio of 0.1. NDT (non-destructive testing) techniques included X-radiography to produce images of the damage. It was also shown how prolonged exposure to the zinc iodide dye penetrant can accelerate the growth of damage in the specimens.

Broughton et. al. [3] have investigated open-hole tension-tension fatigue behaviour of a quasi-isotropic glass-fibre reinforced plastic GFRP laminate under constant amplitude and block amplitude loading. They showed that longitudinal strain, stiffness and surface temperature can be used to assess damage progression and fatigue life, and are potentially suitable for predicting notched fatigue performance. They also showed how the application of various measurement techniques such as fibre-Bragg grating (FBG) and digital image correlation (DIC) can be useful for fatigue damage assessment, and also highlighted localised sub-critical damage at the hole edge.

Other fatigue work involved the investigation of the residual properties of composites after undergoing fatigue. Ambu et. al. [4] carried out a study based on the effects of damage on the residual strength of open-hole laminates subjected to fatigue. They found that DIC proved to be very useful tool in order to clarify the roles played by various failure modes on the residual properties of open-hole laminates.

However this technique isn't useful for predicting with accuracy the stiffness loss of the laminate to failure due to damage initiating mostly at the surface plies, thereby rendering further strain measurements inaccurate.

More recently, high resolution X-ray computed tomography (CT) has become available as an experimental technique. Work by Scott et. al. [5] and Moffat et. al.[6] had proven the capability of this technique to identify damage progression in notched carbon-epoxy specimens under quasi-static loading to failure.

Fatigue damage accumulation at the vicinity of the hole causes a redistribution of stresses giving rise to a notch blunting effect also observed elsewhere in the literature. This results in an increase in the residual strength over untested specimens. However, matrix cracking, fibre breakages and delaminations deteriorate mechanical properties such as stiffness and weakens the composite laminate. Bakis, Simmonds and Stinchcombe [7-10], carried out a systematic study on the effects of stacking sequence, matrix type, and stress ratio on residual strength. They found that for each composite material, a critical cyclic stress level exists where the residual strengths begin to decrease below that of the untested specimens. Residual strength enhancement has also been observed in woven fibre reinforced laminates bearing notches [11]. Wang and Shin [12] also observed notch blunting effects in composite laminates. They based their study on $[0/90]_{4S}$ AS4/PEEK thermoplastic laminates which could be reconsolidated to remove all damage apart from fibre breakages. Other work by Wang [13] included the study of static residual strength comparing scarfed holes with straight sided holes.

To date most of the studies in the literature have concentrated on the macro-scopic effects of fatigue damage on mechanical properties and there have not been many studies into the detailed damage mechanisms and sequence of events occurring. This paper describes and compares the fatigue damage events in open hole tensile tests on various different quasi-isotropic configurations of unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg.

2. Experimental Procedure

Three quasi isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates manufactured from Hexcel's IM7/8552 unidirectional pre-preg material system with nominal ply thickness of 0.125 mm, with stacking

sequence $[45_m/90_m/-45_m/0_m]_{ns}$ were used in this work. Figure 1 shows the specimen geometry.

The first layup, with $m=2$ $n=1$ is defined as a ply scaled laminate due to the plies being blocked together in each orientation, this represents one of two ways of increasing the thickness of the laminate. The second with $m=1$ $n=2$ is defined as a sublaminated scaled laminate due to the repeated sublaminated unit, this will be referred to as the baseline sublaminated case. The third layup is also a variant of the sublaminated configuration but with $m=1$ and $n=4$ so as to increase the total thickness to 4 mm, this will be referred to as the second sublaminated case. From previous quasi-static testing [1], the ply scaled laminate had a delamination dominated failure, whilst the sublaminated scaled laminates had pullout and brittle fibre dominated failure.

Pull-out failure occurs when the fibre failure stresses of the 0° plies are reached during full width delamination of the surface $45/90$ and $-45/0$ interfaces. This partial delamination allows some plies to "pull out" from between each other at the point of fibre failure. If the fibre failure stress has not been reached at the point by which there delamination at the $-45/0$ interface is fully developed across the width then delamination failure back to the specimen grips occurs.

Brittle failure occurs with little or no delamination present. Failure occurs across the full width of the specimen with clean fracture surfaces through the entire laminate with the fracture plane normal to both hole edges and perpendicular to the direction of loading, breaking fibres in every orientation.

The $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_S$ and $[45/90/-45/0]_{2S}$ laminates had a central hole diameter of 3.175 mm, width of 16 mm, thickness of 2 mm, gauge length of 64 mm, and end tab length of 50 mm. The second sublaminated case, $[45/90/-45/0]_{4S}$ had a central hole diameter of 6.35 mm, width of 32 mm and thickness of 4 mm, but used the same gauge length and end tab length as the other two configurations (see figure 1). The thickness, width and hole diameter are therefore scaled up by a factor of 2 from the baseline since previous work by Green et al. [1] shows that this configuration was the smallest specimen size to give a brittle type failure mode in quasi-static tests. In this study the gauge length was reduced in order to save on material costs since it was shown from the static tests that damage did not propagate extensively along the gauge length.

For quasi-static tests, the specimens were loaded at 1mm/min in the 0° direction until failure. A mean static failure load could then be established. Specimens were then loaded in tension-tension fatigue with R=0.1 at 5Hz at various amplitudes to 1E6 cycles or catastrophic failure (represented by a 15% drop in stiffness), whichever occurred first. A number of tests were interrupted at various points as the stiffness dropped with increasing cycles, using 60% severity tests in the ply-level case and 80% severity tests in the first sublaminated case in order to accurately determine a sequence of damage events leading to catastrophic failure in fatigue. Interrupted tests were not carried out for the second sublaminated case as there is very little or no subcritical damage prior to catastrophic failure [14].

The interrupted test specimens for quasi-static loading, and fatigue loading and tests run to 1E6 cycles prior to residual strength testing, were inspected using X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) scanning in order to determine the level of damage in each specimen. CT reconstructions were carried out on each sample after scanning. This enables visualisation of a given sample as a 3D map in which features of interest such as delaminations and matrix cracking could be identified.

Fatigue tests were terminated at 1E6 cycles if no failure occurred, this is termed as a runout. One runout specimen from each configuration was soaked in zinc iodide dye penetrant and the damage was analysed using X-ray CT as per the interrupted fatigue tests. Three further specimens were tested to runout in order to ascertain that the fatigue life indeed exceeded 1E6 cycles for these load levels. Then each runout specimen was tested for residual strength.

3 Static Testing

Five specimens of each layout were loaded to failure using a displacement rate of 1mm/min. Failure was taken as the first significant drop on the load-displacement curve (>5%). Previous analysis of quasi-static tests after failure using various thicknesses and layouts had shown the three distinct failure modes [1] described in section 2:

The tests in this present study represent a configuration from each of the delamination, pullout and brittle failure modes. In all cases quasi-static tests were repeated before commencing the fatigue testing programme.

For the baseline sublaminated case where hole diameter is 3.175 mm, pull-out failure was consistently obtained in each of the five specimens tested. The average failure load was 581 MPa with a CV of 2.9% with load curves shown in fig 2 (a). In the ply level case with hole diameter 3.175 mm a failure load of 446 MPa was recorded with a CV of 4.56%, and load curves shown in fig 2 (b). Interrupted tests of these two cases at 80 and 85% of the static failure load for ply level and first sublaminated level tests respectively show typical damage levels from CT scans in figs 3 and 4.

Three specimens from the second sublaminated configuration were tested. The average static failure load was 475 MPa with a CV of 4.8%. Brittle failure was consistently exhibited for this configuration.

4 Fatigue Testing

For the ply level specimens the fatigue damage in general follows a similar pattern to the quasi-static failure and occurs in the following order:-

- Isolated damage around the hole and free edge of the specimen.
- Damage around the hole at inner delamination regions and damage that is localised around the free edge resulting from full width matrix cracks.
- Damage propagates across the full specimen width from the hole.
- Extensive delamination back to the grips at the -45/0 interface which was the cause of the catastrophic failure.

For the baseline sublaminated specimens, fatigue failure appeared to follow a very similar trend to that of the ply level specimens with delamination dominating in all but the very highest severities (>90%). It is notable that this differed significantly from the quasi-static failure which was dominated by fibre failure (pull-out) with major delamination not progressing along the length of the specimen. It can thus be seen how the role of delamination is critical in the case of fatigue loading, even when it does not dominate in static tests.

As the fatigue severity decreases from 90% to 80% there is a transition from pullout to delamination failure for the baseline sublaminated level specimens. At lower loads the fibre-failure stress is not reached during the development of damage prior to delamination across the full width of specimens. This explains why the fatigue results at 90% tend to shift the SN curve (fig 7) to the left as pullout failure

occurs before delamination in the overall damage development sequence. In all severities lower than 90% we initially see subcritical damage mainly being confined to the outer sublaminates down to a normalised effective modulus of around 0.6 (fig. 5). Then in the latter part of the stiffness drops the damage crosses over into the inner sublaminates regions, this can be shown as a kink in the stiffness curves (fig 5). There is a significant amount of free-edge delamination in comparison to the blocked ply interrupted tests. All of the splits and cracks are accompanied by small local delaminations in the adjacent interfaces and have a similar size to that of the ply thickness.

Figs 5 and 6 show the loss in stiffness as damage develops, characterised as normalised effective modulus, for typical tests at each severity for ply-level and baseline sublaminates testing. Failure was taken as a 15% reduction in the normalised stiffness when plotting the SN curve (fig 7). The significant loss of stiffness relates to the accumulation of damage which is best characterised through interrupted testing as described in the next section.

In fig 5, the stiffness loss from the initial stiffness plateau is more gradual in the baseline sub-laminate layup due to a more progressive sequence of damage events, whereas in fig 6, the stiffness loss in ply level specimens is more abrupt due to a more defined sequence of damage events which are more localised around the hole. In previous experiments the maximum surface temperature was shown to be insignificant but still increased with increasing damage throughout the duration of the decrease in stiffness [15]. Specimens from the second sublaminates configuration were tested at 90, 85, 80 and 75% severity, where all severities tested consistently gave runouts to 1E6 cycles with very little stiffness loss even for the highest of severities tested.

5. Fatigue Interrupted Testing

Several of the fatigue tests were interrupted during the stiffness loss/damage accumulation process. Figures used in this section are typically from tests interrupted at around 0.85 normalised effective modulus as this was used as the failure criterion to generate the SN curves in the previous section.

In the ply level test shown in fig 8 which was at 60% severity there is clear evidence of the delamination propagating at the -45/0 interface. No delamination at this interface is observed in the static interrupted

test at 80% of static load (figure 1). This is the most dominant damage process responsible for the sudden drop in the load in static failure and therefore this isn't observed until catastrophic failure which in fatigue is more of a gradual process.

For the baseline sublaminates level fatigue interrupted test in fig 9, there is extensive delamination at the surface -45/0 interface and also in between the long zero splits at the lower 0° interface to the +45 ply. This occurs relatively early in the drop in stiffness. The -45/0 delamination eventually crosses over into the areas between the zero splits in the most severely damaged interrupted tests. In the dispersed ply specimens, there is a greater degree of global matrix cracking that can initiate delamination damage at the interface.

Interrupted tests were not carried out for the second sublaminates level configuration because all specimens reached 1E6 cycles without loss of stiffness.

6. Residual Strength Testing

The ply level, baseline sublaminates and second sublaminates specimens that reached runout were tested for residual strengths. One specimen from each configuration was used for X-ray CT analysis.

6.1 Ply-level Configuration

The ply level specimens gave consistent runouts at 40% fatigue severity. From the X-ray images in fig.10 at 40% after 1E6 cycles [15] there is relatively little damage. The majority of the damage is in the splitting of the surface plies and matrix cracking of the 90° plies adjacent to the split. There is also some matrix cracking in the -45° directions and some small splits in the 0° direction. There are no delaminations present after 1E6 cycles at 40% except for some small delaminations at the bottom face due to drilling damage. All damage is local to the hole.

The average failure load for the ply level specimens of hole diameter 3.175 mm, was 409 MPa with a coefficient of variation of 4.36% (versus 411 MPa for virgin specimens).

6.2 Baseline Sublaminates Level Configuration

The baseline sublaminates level specimens gave consistent runouts at 55% fatigue severity. The residual tensile strength of these laminates showed a distinct increase following fatigue loading to 1E6 cycles over the quasi-static result.

The average static residual strength was 593 MPa over three specimens with a coefficient of variation of 0.6% (versus 522 MPa for the virgin specimens). Fig. 11. shows the X-ray CT of the baseline sublaminar level laminate at 55% severity after 1E6 cycles. The damage takes the form of distributed matrix cracking in each of the ply orientations throughout the laminate. The damage is slightly more distributed than for the ply level specimen at 40%, but the majority of the damage still occurs around the vicinity of the hole. There are no obvious delaminations in any of the specimens that ran to 1E6 cycles and therefore there is no apparent loss in the stiffness of the specimens as delamination damage accounts for the vast majority of the stiffness loss.

6.3 Second Sublaminar Configuration

The second sublaminar configuration gave consistent runouts even at the highest of severities which giving little or no loss of stiffness. However the X-ray CT image set in figs. 12 and 13 indicates significant matrix cracks and delaminations with different colours allocated to different damage modes and locations. The delaminations tend to occur in the outermost sublaminates. As there are many more plies and interfaces than in the baseline sublaminar case, this delamination doesn't contribute significantly to any loss in stiffness. Tests were carried out for residual strength, using three specimens each for 90 and 85% severity runouts. Static residual strengths at 85% severity were marginally greater than the original quasi static results (492 MPa (3% CV) vs 472 MPa), and similarly for 90% severity (498 MPa (2.2% CV) vs 472 MPa). One test was carried out at 75% severity which showed a residual strength of 509 MPa.

At 90% severity a significant amount of damage is observed and in this case the delaminations propagate back towards the grips. The majority of the damage in the form of delaminations is however mostly confined to the outer sublaminates. At 75% severity only matrix splitting is observed in the specimen with no damage in the form of delaminations.

The failure mode changes from brittle when testing unfatigued specimens in quasi-static loading to pullout after 1E6 cycles as fatigue loading had caused a significant level of delaminations in the outer sublaminates prior to residual strength tests.

Interestingly there was no notable difference in the residual strengths between the tests at 90, 85 or 75%

severity which suggests only a very minimal amount of damage is required to cause a measurable increase in the residual strength.

7. Conclusions

Carbon fibre epoxy laminates of various configurations with a centrally drilled hole, were loaded quasi-statically and in fatigue. In quasi-static ply-level tests, extensive delaminations are observed at the point of failure. Under fatigue loading, the same delamination dominated mode of failure is also observed. For the quasi-static baseline sublaminar level tests, a fibre dominated pullout failure mode is observed, however in fatigue tests, a delamination dominated failure mode is observed in all but the highest of severities tested. Therefore for the baseline sublaminar level tests, a different mode of failure is observed in fatigue tests to those of quasi-static tests. X-ray computed tomography (CT) data of the interrupted tests showed that, initially damage starts to propagate out from the hole edge in terms of matrix cracks and delamination. Asymmetric -45/0 delaminations cause a large drop in effective modulus. This is the dominant failure event for the ply level specimens. The failure events for the ply level specimens are more localised around the hole, giving a more abrupt decrease in stiffness from the initial plateau. For the baseline sublaminar level specimens, damage occurs in the outer sublaminates first and then passes through into the central sublaminates with a greater degree of distributed matrix cracking. This gives rise to a more progressive damage sequence leading to failure. Run-outs for the baseline sublaminar level tests were each subjected to quasi-static loading to failure to reveal an increase in static residual strength properties. A significant degree of localised matrix cracking was observed from the X-ray CT scans which caused blunting of stress concentrations due to the hole.

A third layup, with specimen dimensions scaled up by a factor of 2 in the thickness, width, and hole diameter was tested. This configuration was shown to give brittle failure in quasi-static loading in previous studies. This case gave runouts for all severities tested in fatigue. A fatigue residual strength study showed that the failure mode changes from brittle when testing unfatigued specimens in quasi-static loading to pullout after 1E6 cycles. The residual strength properties for this configuration were shown to be only a slight increase on the quasi-static strengths, within the upper range of the scatter. The residual strengths appeared to be consistent for

runouts at three different severities each of which had varying levels of damage.

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Figures

Figure 1. Showing the specimen geometry.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Load-Displacement curves for (a) Baseline sublaminate level tests with hole diameter 3.175 mm and (b) Ply level tests with hole diameter 3.175 mm.

Figure 3. X-ray CT scan images from a ply-level test interrupted at 80% static load, showing the damage initiation (from top left), the global damage pattern, +45 splits, 90 splits, -45 splits and zero splits.

Figure 4. X-ray CT scan images from a baseline sublaminate level test with hole diameter 3.175 mm, interrupted at 85% static load, showing the damage initiation (from top left), the global damage pattern, +45 splits, 90 splits, -45 splits and zero splits.

Figure 5. Typical fatigue stiffness curves at each severity for the baseline sublaminde level test program with hole diameter of 3.175 mm.

Figure 6. Typical fatigue stiffness curves at each severity for the ply-level test program with hole diameter of 3.175 mm.

Figure 7. Plot showing both ply and baseline sublaminde SN curves for hole diameter of 3.175 mm with runouts indicated using arrows.

Figure 8. X-ray CT images from an interrupted test for a blocked ply laminate at 60% severity.

Figure 9. X-Ray CT Images from a baseline sublaminde interrupted test at 80% severity with an approximate load drop of 15%.

Fig 10. Typical ply level specimen with hole diameter of 3.175 mm, +45, 90, -45 and 0 degree splits after 1E6 Cycles at 40% severity prior to static residual strength test.

Fig 12. X-ray CT slices for a second sublaminat level fatigue test at 85% severity.

Figure 11. X-ray CT slices for the baseline sublaminat level fatigue test at 55% severity.

Fig 13. X-ray CT slices for a second sublaminat level fatigue test at 90% severity.